

SHERPA
Rural Science-Society-Policy
Interfaces

D2.5. SHERPA WEBSITE

DECEMBER 2019

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1. Introduction

This document presents the first version of the SHERPA website that is publicly launched in December 2019 during month 3 of the project, fulfilling the requirements of the Deliverable 2.5 – Website.

2. SHERPA Website

The SHERPA website is the **primary hub of information for SHERPA**, providing a 'one-stop shop' for resources, news, and key information on relevant initiatives. As indicated in the D2.1 Strategy for project Stakeholder Engagement, Communication and Dissemination, the website is hosted at www.rural-interfaces.eu and coded using a leading content management systems - Wordpress. The website is **hosted independently on the computer servers of AEIDL**, allowing flexibility for web-development and dynamic functionality.

2.1. First version of the SHERPA website

In Month 3, the SHERPA project is at the very beginning of its implementation. Accordingly, this first version of the website displays relevant information about the project that is currently available such as a brief description of the purpose of the project, key resources, SHERPA events, the Newsletter and Social Media channels.

This first version of the website can be considered as a 'web holder' that will evolve over the next months by developing further a use-friendly structure for displaying and communicating all project outputs, and by enhancing the design of the SHERPA website (see section 3 for the detailed time plan). The figure below presents the layout of the first version of the SHERPA website.

Figure 1: First version of the SHERPA website

MULTI-ACTOR PLATFORMS (MAPs)

SHERPA will implement 40 Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) across the EU. They will be the core forum for two-way exchanges of ideas for co-learning and co-creation of knowledge at regional levels among a wide variety of stakeholders.

KEY RESOURCES

- **SHERPA POSITION PAPERS**
Available from October 2020
 Papers that will formulate recommendations for informing the development of future rural policies based on the evidence and results of previous research projects and local views from the MAPs.
- **STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT TOOLS**
Available in January 2020
 Repository of main tools that support the engagement of stakeholder in the project MAPs.
- **SHERPA ONLINE REPOSITORY**
Available in October 2020
 A web crawling tool that will allow the retrieval of scientific data and information relevant to rural research from past and ongoing research projects.

OUR EVENTS

SHERPA will implement many events to ensure the participation of all key stakeholders in the project.

PAST EVENT

Kick Off meeting (21-22 October 2019)

UPCOMING EVENT

Training of MAP facilitators and monitors (16 January 2020)

SUBSCRIBE TO THE NEWSLETTER

Yes, I want subscribe right now!

KEEP IN TOUCH

DONT MISS ANYTHING ABOUT SHERPA !

Project coordinator:
 Olivier Chartier and Elodie Salle (ECORYS) - sherpa@ecorys.com

General contact:
 info@rural-interfaces.eu

Social media channels:

2.2. Website timeplan for further updates

The approach of the project is to work on the website throughout the project implementation and maintain its functionalities after the finalisation of the project. All key information and outputs from the project will be uploaded on the website as soon as they become available. The next updates on the website will be related to the further elaboration of its structure (development of sections, and subsections), integrating all the elements indicated in the D2.1 Strategy for project Stakeholder Engagement, Communication and Dissemination, such as:

- an overview of the SHERPA project and countries covered;
- a gallery for the multimedia material, including a series of mini-videos;
- the latest news and blogs posts on the project activities will be showcased, as well as a searchable calendar of project activities and events;
- Information about SHERPA events;
- A Press corner with live feed to the latest project social media posts, the Rural Interfaces blog, press releases and the archive of the published newsletters;
- Key Resources, including project materials, i.e. the online stakeholder engagement tool, and the repository of past and on-going research outcomes relating to rural areas;
- A dedicated section for the MAPs which will provide information about the focus of each of the project's MAP, their activities, dates for planned events, outcomes, etc;
- The contact details.

The timeplan presented below outlines two main stages in the workplan for the next updated versions of the website, namely i) develop the structure and final design of the website and ii) ongoing upload of information and web maintenance.

Table 1: Website timeplan

Indicative deadline	Step
15 Jan 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Finalisation of the website structure to be implemented in the updated version of the website;
29 Feb 2020	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the updated version of website with the agree website structure and design;
30 Sept 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing maintenance and upload of information

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